

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

CHAOS THEORY AND CRISIS COMMUNICATION COMMUNICATION MANAGEMENT IN UNCERTAINTY ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract

Chaos Theory states that in real life, as in science, there is a crisis point in a chain of events that turns small changes into big problems. According to this theory, which is generally used to solve complex problems and sometimes gives very good results, the problem is first broken down and the simpler sub-problems that emerge are examined. Then, the solutions of these sub-problems are combined to create the solution to the entire problem.

One of the most important changes brought by chaos theory is unpredictable determinism. No matter how well we model the structure of the system, even a mistake we make will lead to completely wrong results in the prediction. In the modern age, order and chaos together form the new normal. In the environment of uncertainty created by this normal, the chaos approach comes to the fore for institutions to adapt to change and cope with crises. Adapting to the conditions of the new normal is very important in terms of sustainability.

In this study, a conceptual review of chaos and chaos theory was conducted, and the relationship between crisis communication and the chaos approach was examined. The central role of communication in solving problems faced by organizations in an environment of uncertainty is discussed, and how crisis communication is viewed in light of chaos theory is discussed.

Keywords: Meaning of chaos, Chaos Theory, Chaos and crisis, Crisis communication, Uncertainty, Risk

Introduction

The United States National Intelligence Council published a report titled *Global Trends 2025: A Changing World in 2008*. According to this report, it was emphasized that the world would face turmoil, chaos and violence soon. Uncertainties in the international system at the global level, the intensification of terrorism and violence, economic and political instabilities, epidemics, unilateral policies and increasing nationalism have deepened uncertainty. According to Kotler (2017), in this environment of uncertainty, the business world will struggle to exist in a more complex structure rather than having a certain predictability. This complex structure, increasing uncertainty and turmoil constitute the new normal. The new normal forces companies and states to develop more dynamic and new strategic approaches. Since the new normal creates insecurity, uncertainty and disorder, it poses a great challenge to companies and states. In the century we are in, societies are undergoing very rapid change and transformation. In this wave of change, traditional institutional structures have to transform themselves and adapt to the new normal [9]. The speed of change also makes the measures to be taken against chaos in the new normal complex and limited. The increasing uncertainty and dynamism of change with globalization force societies to face more complex and chaotic developments. Institutions face more risks in the uncertain environment created by the new normal. Chaos does not refer to a situation that must be endured for a certain period, but to a continuous and permanent structure, namely the new normal. Chaos theory brings a different perspective to crisis communication by offering a more holistic and dynamic perspective. Since crisis manage-

ment is largely a communicative process, crisis communication plays a central role in crisis management and can be an effective mechanism in overcoming crises. It contributes greatly to the restructuring and improvement of institutions' relations with the external environment [2].

The concept of chaos

"In terms of its literal meaning, chaos evokes expressions such as "complexity, disorder, uncertainty" and even "anarchy" in everyday language. The concept comes from the Greek word "Khaos" meaning "void, gap, boundarylessness". While the term chaos means chaos in everyday language, in the scientific approach it means order within disorder. In the traditional scientific approach, chaos and order are seen as opposites. According to chaos theory, order and chaos are "mirror reflections of each other". Chaos describes an unpredictable, regular disorder in which behavioral patterns emerge in irregular but similar ways. Kaya (2021) also describes chaos as the twin of order. According to him, order is what is not chaos; chaos is what is not orderly. "Order and chaos are modern twins. They were born in the midst of the disintegration and collapse of the world that was neither divinely ordered, nor random, that was aware of the necessity nor randomness, that simply existed - and did not think of its own existence. Here we are, having difficulty defining this thoughtless and careless world that existed before the bifurcation of order and chaos in its own terms. The only alternative to order is chaos." Chaos does not mean a completely incomprehensible and random confusion. The chaos is the irregular, unpredictable behavior of deterministic, nonlinear dynamic systems. Chaotic structure, whose behavior and movements are unpredictable and exhibit

a new movement each time, is associated with nondynamic systems. While linear systems are predictable and have a systemic structure in their relationship with the environment, chaotic systems exhibit a non-linear, unpredictable, process-based structure. Chaotic structures have a delicate sensitivity to the starting point. Therefore, predictions about the future are not possible without knowing the initial conditions. Chaotic systems contain an order within themselves as well as unpredictability and uncertainty. Many mathematicians state that non-linear situations can be a surprising source of order. Non-linear situations create chaos and non-linear situations calm chaos. Although chaos contains elements of chance, it is not a random disorder. Chaos theory tries to understand the behaviors of non-linear systems that do not emerge in a cause-and-effect relationship. When these systems are considered as a whole, they reflect certain patterns and behaviors. However, the future trends of chaotic systems cannot be predicted by looking at their past behaviors. Chaos is not a random system, but a structure that is both deterministic and unpredictable. Priscilla Murphy mentioned in his book that the first important study on chaos theory was done by the French mathematician Henri Poincaré in the 19th century. According to him, there are no permanent solutions in multivariable systems. One of the tiny points that escape our attention causes such big and important results that we say that this result emerged by chance. If we knew the laws of nature and the state of the universe at the beginning, we could also predict exactly what state the universe would be in at one of the later moments following its initial state. A tiny error in the initial conditions will cause a huge error in the final event. In this case, it is not possible to predict what will happen. In his book, Murphy noted the following about American mathematician and meteorologist Edward Lorenz's study: his study in 1961 made a significant contribution to the development of chaos theory. He made observations that are referred to as the sensitive dependence of meteorological changes on initial conditions and made the weather simplest with numerical simulation, expressing it as a few functions with respect to time. The principle of sensitive dependence on the initial state was demonstrated in his work. It was assumed that weather events could be predicted in the long term with a deterministic approach. He took a shortcut without entering the data after the comma into the computer program he used for weather forecasting. Completely different results emerged from the previous data. Very small differences between the program inputs changed the results. Very small effects could create big results. He described this situation with the metaphor of the butterfly effect. Accordingly, an insignificant air movement can have increasing power and turn into a movement affecting the continents. Air movements express a non-linear system. The shape likened to a butterfly in his work expresses that there is "a solid and beautiful structure within an irregular data flow".

Weather forecasting, the first field where computers were used in modeling complex systems, played a leading role. Chaos theory later began to be applied to various fields in social sciences, from management to psychology, from politics to public relations and crisis communication. The theory reveals the characteristics

of process-related factors, unlike the result-oriented, predictive structure of the deterministic paradigm. Accordingly, chaos theory expresses a non-linear, dynamic process-based structure instead of a result-oriented long-term, zero-sum, linear approach [4].

Basic concepts of chaos theory

The theory of chaos has developed with the contributions of many researchers such as Henri Poincaré, Edward Lorenz, and Mandelbrot. It has created a new paradigm that will contribute to the understanding of complex structures, especially against the assumptions of the deterministic, linear traditional paradigm. Some of the basic assumptions of chaos theory can be listed as follows:

1. **The principle of sensitivity to the initial state:** This principle, identified with Lorenz's work, refers to the conditions at the moment when the butterfly first flaps its wings in the butterfly effect metaphor. The important point here is that a chaotic event is sensitively connected to the initial state. This metaphor emphasizes the openness and sensitivity to small variance effects that cannot be understood and measured by traditional methods in complex systems. Most nonlinear systems act according to this principle. Since there are many variables in chaotic systems, the smallest change at the initial point, the smallest element can cause major changes in the system. Since chaotic systems are dynamic and irregular, they respond to their environment in an unstable manner. In fact, there is a causality here. Unforeseen situations can arise from any phenomenon in delicate balance as a result of a triggering of that phenomenon. They interact with their environment and experiences are learned. Thus, when the delicate balance between the internal forces that structure the system and the external forces that form their environment is disrupted, stress is experienced. This balance, the relationship between stability and instability is often called the "edge of chaos". In other words, some changes that are actually instantaneous can bring major results/changes in the future.

2. **Bifurcation:** It refers to a tendency towards instability that can suddenly change the structure, character and direction of the chaotic system. In such a case, the system reorganizes itself by moving to a point that may be similar to the previous one or very different – expressing the situation where a certain parameter belonging to a phenomenon or entity passes to a new value at a critical point, the balance point disappears with the choice made and it moves towards a new balance. Bifurcation often means having more alternatives than dilemmas. At this point, linearity is broken and the beginning of a new linear system is formed, which will continue until a new bifurcation point. In this sense, bifurcation is the simplest example of a discontinuity. All complex systems have the potential to bifurcate. While bifurcation can be predicted, its results cannot. Even the slightest choice in a linear system creates bifurcation. Because as the system moves in another direction, there will be other bifurcations on the path that changes with the choice made at the previous bifurcation point. In other words, different bifurcation points, or different futures, will occur depending on the choice made. While bifurcation can be predicted, its results cannot be

predicted. All complex systems have the potential to bifurcate. However, when systems reach higher and more complex levels and when the level of dependency, connectivity and environmental change increases, bifurcation becomes more likely.

3. **Strange attractors:** "System behavior tends to be influenced by different attractors". These are complex geometric structures or curves that occur in chaotic systems. Attractors are shapes formed in the phase space of the motion in dynamic systems. They limit the movement of the system in space-time. Strange attractors are sensitively dependent on initial conditions.

4. **Fractals:** It is derived from the subject of measuring complex systems according to chaos theory. "Fractal is a word that replaces a tool to be used to describe, calculate and think about irregular, fragmented, broken and discontinuous shapes." They are geometric shapes that repeat themselves or scale similarly, they look the same at different scales. This means that you can zoom in on a fractal and see the same patterns repeated over and over again. A fractal is any object with fractional dimensions, so it has a precise mathematical definition. First of all, fractals have infinite symmetry. Fractals are not linear systems; they are mathematical curves like spirals and helices.

The reason why fractals are not completely identified with chaos is that fractals themselves are not chaotic. One of the mathematical ways to state one of the connections between chaos theory and fractals is that the center of attraction (we can think of the center of attraction as the motion of a planet orbiting a nucleus of attraction) with fractal boundaries exhibits chaotic behavior.

5. **Self-organization:** It is a process resulting from the interactions of the components in a chaotic system. It is a situation that arises from the relationships between the elements of the system and develops spontaneously. In chaotic systems, the structure that seems irregular has the ability to organize itself spontaneously. Thus, in dynamic systems, the self-organization resulting from the interaction between the elements of the system renews the continuity of the system.

Non-linear systems create uncertainty because they exhibit regular irregularities. When uncertainty increases, various risks come into play. In such an environment, the management of uncertainty becomes more important [5].

Uncertainty and risk

Today, the concept of risk has become a concept used in many areas such as economics and international relations, especially within the chaotic uncertainty created by modernity, and is used to refer to a wide variety of situations. The concept of risk did not exist in traditional societies, in the Middle Ages. Risk has become a defining feature of modern society with industrialization and globalization. The notion of risk cannot be separated from the ideas of probability and uncertainty. Risk describes dangers that are effectively evaluated by considering future possibilities. Capitalism cannot be thought of without risk in this context. Ozdemir states that "the risks of modernity are the product of industrialization and systematically intensify as it globalizes.

With globalization, risks no longer belong to the starting point. International problems such as global terrorism and financial crises are now progressing towards an uncontrollable point. Modern society tries to distribute responsibility by spreading risk to various stakeholders. This causes the causal relationship between the act and the perpetrator to disappear and the responsibility for the risk to become unclear".

According to Ozdemir, risk is a modern approach that aims to control and predict the undesirable future consequences of human actions that have become more radical with modernization. Stating that risk is about moving from one position to another, he says that 'mobility in modern societies increases risk areas'. Risk is a phenomenon that cannot be considered separately from uncertainty. Risk and uncertainty are among the most important features that define modern societies. Rapid developments in communication technologies and globalization have created significant changes in the relationships of organizations with their target audiences and environments. Especially in times of crisis, the turbulence experienced by organizations makes it possible for the dimensions of the crisis to expand in a short time. Crises can quickly reach a global dimension. This fluidity between the local and the global makes it necessary for businesses to redefine their environment. The most important feature that defines this new environment is uncertainty. Ozdemir defines uncertainty as follows while describing the chaos experienced by modernity: "Ambiguity, which means that an object or an event can be put into more than one category, is a disorder specific to language, that is, the failure of the naming (classification) function performed by language. The basic symptom of this disorder is the sharp discomfort we feel when we cannot read a certain situation correctly and cannot choose between alternative actions." Stating that uncertainty specific to language is the normal state of language, he explains this seemingly dilemma-like structure as follows: "It is because of the anxiety that arises in this situation and the indecision that follows, that we experience ambiguity as a disorder; at that time, we either blame the language we use for being inadequate or ourselves for using the language incorrectly. However, ambiguity is not the result of a pathology lying in the language or in the use of language; it is an ordinary element of linguistic practice" [10].

Although uncertainty seems to be a situation that threatens institutions and businesses, it also offers new opportunities. Uncertainty is also a weapon of modern man. In postmodern societies, uncertainty is no longer a threat but also a harbinger of new opportunities. Thus, in the postmodern world where order and disorder are intertwined, chaotic systems constitute a threat element and a state of probability that contains new opportunities. There are also opportunities and threats for organizations and states in a chaotic structure. The business world feels threatened in terms of the sustainability of the system in the face of uncertainty and unpredictability. Fighting uncertainty is among the most important topics in the business world. Companies have to review their strategies in order to better manage risks and chaotic structures in an environment of uncertainty. Kotler says that today and, in the future, perhaps asking what

a company owns or produces will not be as important as questions about the company's ability to detect turbulence, predict chaos and manage risks. Institutions face constant uncertainty in an environment of chaos. Kotler lists the changes in the management approach in this environment as follows [11].

- Analysis loses its own priorities,
- Cause and effect relationship loses its meaning,
- Long-term planning becomes impossible,
- The concept of vision begins to lose its meaning,
- Cultures that are strong and have a constant consensus begin to become dangerous.

“Identifying and managing risks is not a simple task. In order to predict risks in advance; it is necessary to develop scenarios and strategies, evaluate opportunities, and teach leaders to gradually instill a new discipline. When these new and necessary behaviors become part of daily decision-making processes, they create a culture that chaos cannot shake. Companies that follow this path will achieve success in an era of turmoil”. There is constant chaos in the modern era. This situation is a nightmare for institutions and states. However, it is necessary to live in a constant state of chaos and be ready for the opportunities that will arise in this chaos. According to Taylor, “The only alternative to order is chaos. The other of order is the undetermined and unpredictable dirty air. The other is uncertainty, which is the source and archetype of all fears. Without the negativity of chaos, there is no positivity in order. There is no order without chaos.” Being ready for this new normal is extremely important for institutions and businesses to continue their existence. The necessity of adapting to uncertainty without any starting point forces organizations to move to a more flexible and dynamic structure.

Uncertainties that occur in a continuous chaotic environment highlight how businesses will proceed. At this point, Kotler (2017) puts forward the concept of chaos management and explains it as follows: “It is a systematic approach to detect and analyze turbulence and chaos, and to respond appropriately to turbulence and the chaos it creates.” In the chaos approach, businesses should try to adapt to the rapid change in the environment with a dynamic and holistic approach and create a strong communication mechanism. The most basic element of the chaos management strategy is the development of the most likely scenarios that the company will encounter together with all decision-making units of the management. Preparations should be made by creating the worst, most expected and best-case scenarios. The aim of management in a chaotic environment is to create a flexible, strong and durable company that has the ability to survive and grow. In the modern world where risk and uncertainty prevail, crisis is not a temporary situation but a constantly existing phenomenon. ‘The continuity of being in crisis’ is a reality of the new normal. In this new normal, the approach offered by chaos theory for managing crises offers new perspectives to organizations [6].

Chaos and crisis communication

Crisis is generally defined as the stress caused by a failure in a system. A crisis is the perception of an

unpredictable event that threatens the expectations of stakeholders regarding environmental, security, health and economic issues and can seriously affect the performance of an institution and create negative results. According to Brown, to talk about a crisis, the following three conditions must occur together:

- The reputation of the organization is shaken
- The time for solving the problem is very limited
- It occurs at an unexpected time by the organization

Brown (2022) defines a crisis as “a situation where events challenge what is accepted as normality and routine actions no longer bring the results we were accustomed to in the past”. According to chaos theory, a crisis is a bifurcation point in the system, or a fundamental disruption of the structure that is separated from the previous state, a radical change in the character and structure of the system. According to chaos theory, the high level of complexity and environmental dependency of organizations makes it more likely for them to encounter crisis situations. Chaos also refers to “interlocking crises. Crises are more understandable situations in terms of their causes compared to chaos. While there is a state of transience and manageability in crises, there is a drift into chaos. Crisis communication has an important place in chaos theory. A sudden crisis that may occur in organizations, combines many variables in a chaotic interaction. Crises develop in the form of a complex series of events with an increasing speed over time. Institutions have the power to influence and direct events at the beginning of a crisis, that is, in the acute period, within the life cycle of crises. When organizations cannot manage the process correctly in this critical period, the crisis escalates and the capacity to be managed begins to be lost. It exhibits a similar structure to chaotic systems with the phase of getting out of control. In a global environment where organizations are heavily affected by the environment, crises related to environmental dependency and change are generally defined as system bifurcation in chaos theory. Since businesses are open to environmental effects, the complexity of the external environment affecting institutions creates uncertainty. Especially with globalization, crises are not temporary but permanent. Since organizations are not closed systems, they are open to the effects of the environment. In such an environment, a small crisis can turn into a big problem. Crises act as a bifurcation in an organization in the face of new and unexpected situations. It is difficult to implement change in a chaotic system as long as events are dependent on strange attractors. Murphy emphasizes that the following should be taken into consideration when intervening in a crisis in organizations with high uncertainty and instability in terms of chaos theory [4]:

- Change should develop within the target public. It cannot be imposed from outside, but the seeds of change can be planted
- The most effective intervention in a crisis occurs when a group is on its way to disrupting its stability.
- In such crisis points, rapid action should be taken so that events do not take their own shape.

According to Demirtash, chaos theory provides a very useful analogy for the relations between organizations and their publics rather than a practical solution source. It helps to structure problems when there is insufficient information about cause-and-effect relationships and when social actors act unpredictably. Crises and disasters reveal chaotic situations; they show the complex relationships between human and natural systems. Therefore, understanding the relationship between cause and effect, the results of decisions and actions is a complex process. The boundaries between human action or inaction and the development of crisis phenomena are blurred due to increasing complexity. Many stable systems can be affected by small changes. The butterfly effect metaphor is at the center of this effect. According to Demirtash, chaos theory provides a powerful framework for understanding system collapse during organizational crisis. Chaos theory is also related to organizational crisis in terms of communicational dimensions with the concepts of system stability, instability, decline and renewal. Thus, a broad conceptualization beyond the traditional crisis communication and strategic response framework of public relations is in question. Communication processes play a central role in routine organizational activities and chaotic crisis points. In the communication processes of organizations, minor communication failures and misinterpretation of messages can lead to chaotic results. Within the framework of the principle of sensitive dependence on the initial state, a small movement within the system can create a butterfly effect and cause a crisis. The accident of NASA's Challenger space shuttle due to an error in the communication process is also an important example of the butterfly effect. When systems exhibit chaotic behavior, it may become impossible to correctly assess the risk related to the crisis. Chaos theory enables the system to renew itself by stepping in within the context of the principle of self-organization when the system enters a crisis and amidst the destructive effects of the crisis. This principle is noteworthy in that it is encountered more in natural disasters. According to chaos theory, when there is a fork in the system, self-organization occurs. The aim here is to ensure the continuity of the system. In the chaotic situation created by a natural disaster, people organize themselves and create a resistance and structure. Such an organization was in question during the September 11 attacks. After the Southern California earthquake in 1987, when the traffic lights did not work, people showed the same behavior of obeying the rules. In chaotic systems, the organization can exhibit self-organization behavior as a flexibility that can ensure the continuity of the system despite encountering various attractors and factors. According to him, self-organization is a semi-evolutionary principle. Accordingly, although the action in the chaotic structure appears spontaneous, it occurs in a certain order as a feature of nonlinear systems [7].

Liska and others also found that self-organization stood out as a crisis response strategy in the Kingston coal ash spill crisis. In the study of Sellnow and others, it is stated that self-organization stood out as a crisis response strategy in the flood disaster in the Red River Valley in 1997. Especially crises caused by natural disasters have typical features for non-dynamic systems.

As seen in the examples, fractals, attractors, bifurcations and especially self-organization offer a more explanatory conceptual framework in such crises. Some theorists describe self-organization as anti-chaos with a mirror image. Accordingly, disordered systems can spontaneously reach a higher-order stage. Liska also defined order and chaos as the only alternatives to each other. In this sense, self-organization emerges as an order originating from the internal dynamics of the system within chaos. Chaos theory offers a broad perspective to analyze crisis communication beyond the traditional linear cause-effect approach in post-crisis situations. Chaos theory allows for unifying relationships such as the change of values and the reorganization of cooperation relationships; it provides a metaphor that captures the unpredictable and non-linear nature of crises. Since a small fluctuation in the system causes chaos, chaos theory has been applied to crisis communication as a method for both restoring the system and understanding unexpected interruptions or crises. When there is a fork in chaotic structures, crisis managers must collect information and transform it into shareable knowledge to protect target publics from the damage of the crisis. The ultimate goal is to see new organizational patterns that explain the systemic conditions related to the crisis. Attractors are social acceptances, values and principles that bring people together for a common purpose. According to him, the most important attractor for individuals and institutions is the need for meaning. Similarly, one of the first things to do in crisis situations is to present something meaningful to target publics. When the reason for the action is not understood, stakeholders may misinterpret messages or cause undesirable meanings. According to Sellnow and others, the chaotic crisis view is that it is not possible to accurately predict or foresee complex and dynamic system behavior. According to them, a crisis represents a point of imbalance in the system, a bifurcation in routines, procedures, assumptions and other structures. The self-organization process can occur after the bifurcation. Self-organization emerges through strange attractors and fractals and eventually recreates the system at a higher level of order and complexity. In chaotic systems, institutions must be able to adapt to change in an environment of increasing uncertainty. Change requires a dynamic structure and flexibility. While organizations are under the influence of non-dynamic systems, they are stuck between changing and drifting by adapting to change. The chaos approach says that opposites can exist at the same time. For example, "businesses need to be both global and local, centralized and decentralized. They should plan for the long term but still be flexible" [3].

Result

In a constantly chaotic environment, crises have a global character. Thanks to the rapid development of information and technology, turmoil in any company can have a disruptive effect on economies, and a dissatisfied customer can turn branded corporate companies upside down. In the Middle East, a fire lit by someone in Tunisia first spread to many countries and triggered the social actions known as the Arab Spring. Especially with the effect of globalization, crises and chaos can spread very quickly with the butterfly effect. Since

businesses and institutions are open organizations, they show very sensitive reactions to the environment. Crisis communication also interacts intensively with target publics and stakeholders. Since this interaction is not independent of the environment, institutions need to be careful about all risk and potential crisis areas in their management processes. Sometimes, an unimportant phenomenon integrates with a wave of social reaction and enters a drift in chaotic behavior. Chaos management envisages a structure that requires flexibility, dynamism and durability. Due to unpredictability, it requires a high level of adaptation to change and a process-based structure. When making short-, medium- and long-term strategic management plans, companies should develop a strategic chaos approach within the framework of chaos theory, and create flexible, situation-specific scenarios and plans against all possibilities. Chaos theory has an important place in minimizing the effects of crises by shaping and directing them during their development phase. In the new normal, institutions should dynamically address the public opinion and the environment in order to better understand the behavioral models and regular irregularities revealed by chaos theory. The chaos approach provides a framework for companies to survive in this uncertainty by developing the ability to predict crises before they occur. According to chaos theory, it is possible to direct the crisis before it escalates in the initial period of the crisis. For this, institutions need to be flexible enough to respond to uncertainties faster and adapt to change with a holistic approach. Chaos theory enables institutions and organizations to address the crisis with a more holistic perspective with the concepts put forward by the theory, in addition to traditional crisis communication methods in the chaotic structure. The theory does not exclude traditional methods, but offers a new perspective to survive in a continuous crisis environment with them.

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